

ON THE ACCELERATED TESTING OF GRAPHITE/EPOXY COUPONS

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ABSTRACT

Aircraft structures should be designed to be damage tolerant and durable. In order to meet these goals for advanced composite structures, it is essential to determine the damage growth rate and related residual strengths for structures undergoing a service environment (i.e., spectrum loading, temperature, humidity, chemical degradation). Realistic testing of the coupled behavior of the components of the environment is impractical since the test duration would be the lifetime of the aircraft. In addition, the random nature of the environment precludes attainment of any degree of certainty unless an "expected worst" case is used.

In order to assure structural serviceability, integrity, and durability, it is therefore necessary to develop a rational accelerated testing procedure for graphite/epoxy. One of the objectives of this paper is to present such a rational and to discuss qualitatively its limitations.

INTRODUCTION

Within recent years, significant changes have occurred in the philosophy toward achieving structural safety and durability. Basically, the new requirements are geared to the development of structures that are capable of accommodating flaws induced either in manufacture or in service, i.e., damage tolerance, and that have, in addition, an economic life in excess of the expected operational life, i.e., durability. To accomplish this end, the technologies of structural analysis/design, fracture mechanics (life analysis), structural inspection (NDE), fabrication, and qualification testing are integrally coupled. This state of quality is then maintained by scheduled in-service inspection and maintenance. This philosophy is well underway to being implemented for metallic structures.

The above philosophy includes, in addition to the goal of structural integrity (strength, rigidity, damage tolerance, and durability), an objective of Operational Readiness. This Operational Readiness is achieved through a design and manufacturing process that results in reduced structural maintenance, and through a Force Management Plan that provides for scheduled inspections and for scheduled economic repairs or replacement. Accomplishment of this broad objective will provide what may be loosely classified as "Serviceability."

In addressing the application of these "Serviceability" requirements to composites, we must ask these searching questions:

- What is the "Effect of Defects" on safety and durability?
- Do Flaws grow? - If so, how catastrophically?
- What type of flaws are critical?
- What is the capability of NDE to detect flaws?
- Can the residual strength of an element with a known flaw be predicted?
- Can damage tolerant structures be designed knowing the probable presence of detectable and nondetectable flaws?

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- Knowing the above, can we define a defect "Accept/Reject Criteria" for fabrication and field inspection.

To answer these questions a program entitled "Serviceability" was formulated to provide insight into all of these questions. Included were efforts to evaluate NDE techniques; to develop and evaluate theoretical procedures for predicting the residual strength of flawed structure; to experimentally evaluate the effect of various flaws on damage propagation and residual strength; and to develop an accept/reject criteria. Hopefully this and subsequent efforts will lead to a capability to design and adequately inspect structures that will assure a high level of damage tolerant structures and meet established safety and durability requirements. This paper will describe a portion of the effort of this Serviceability program aimed at the development of experimental information on the growth of flaws and their influence on residual strength. Special emphasis will be given to how the real time environmental matrix of load, temperature, and moisture was reduced and compressed in order to permit an accelerated one life simulation test to be conducted in 24 hours.

For this experimental coupon test program to have the broadest system application and relevancy, an attempt was made to bound the problem by developing a realistic but yet an "expected worst case" set of test conditions. It was postulated, that if serious serviceability implications were demonstrated, then any concerned designer would be alerted to a potential problem that would require his attention and of the necessity to evaluate his special case. Conversely, if no implications of criticality were found as the result of conducting a worst case test, then most serious concerns would largely be obviated.

TEST OBJECTIVES AND PHILOSOPHY

The paramount objective is to design an accelerated test program and procedure that would induce flaw damage growth in the coupon closely representative of that incurred by a real structure under a real time "expected worst case" environment so that residual strength values can be obtained. While this will not be fully validated in the program, valuable data on the characteristics of flaw growth and strength degradation will be acquired. A second objective was the evaluation of two selected NDE techniques (pulse-echo ultrasonics and acoustic emission) on their capability to monitoring flaw growth, and to characterize the flaw in size, shape and volumetric location.

To philosophically bound the problem and to establish this "expected worst case," several coupon design and test parameters were bounded to produce the most adverse environmental test condition. The following describes the selection of these "worst case" parameters. The two laminates selected were a quasi-isotropic (0/+45/90) and a (0₂/+45) fiber orientation. Inclusion of 90° plies in the first laminate will involve a ply failure at lower strains than will occur in the latter laminate and should therefore cover the possibility of coupling ply damage with flaw growth. Also, a stacking sequence was selected for each coupon test case that would induce the highest transverse, through-the-thickness, stresses, hence producing a stress state most adverse to flaw growth. The test environmental conditions of load, temperature, and absorbed moisture level were selected to provide realistic but severe service simulation. The absorbed moisture level and through-the-thickness distribution to be used results from many years of aircraft operation at a severe state-side basing and then one year of basing on a South Pacific Island demonstrated to be the worst, worst-case. All wet coupons are preconditioned to this worst case before testing. The highest temperature results from supersonic flight and the lowest temperature excursion from arctic basing. The loading environment utilizes a vertical tail spectrum that sees fully reversed load and hence a stress ratio (R) of -1.0. Also the maximum load applied is limit design load, where limit load is 2/3 of ultimate allowable (.80% of average ultimate stress). This combination of R = -1.0 and limit load is believed most likely to produce the worst cyclic load condition. Flaws were determined from an industry-wide survey and screened for the four worst, based on their likelihood of occurrence and presumed criticality. These will be further screened in the test program to determine the most critical flaw. For this flaw, a more in-depth test investigation will be made. Flaws will also be placed in the most adverse locations through the thickness.

TEST PLAN

The three types of coupons, shown in Fig. 1, were selected to represent tension, compression, and bolted structure. These would provide for varied stress states during cyclic loading and the residual strength tests. As will be described later, flaws were defined for each coupon type on the basis of their criticality for each type of loading. The test matrix shown in Figure 2 begins with a screening of four flaw types at one flaw size (as shown by test series T₁ and T₂) followed by further screening of the two most critical flaws at a second flaw size (T₃ and T₄). Based on these results, an in-depth evaluation of the critical flaw type will be made (T₇ through T₁₀). Combinations of room temperature (R.T.) and elevated test temperature (Hot) with dry and wet moisture conditioned coupons are to be made, with the greatest emphasis being placed on elevated temperature wet. Also to gain some insight into the effect that very low temperatures have on degradation, some -65°F residual strength tests (T₅ and T₆) are planned. These tests are a cursory attempt to answer the question: "do flaws grow more readily in a dry/cold brittle matrix as opposed to growth in a hot/wet rubbery matrix?" In addition, an alternate,

FIGURE 1 COUPON CONFIGURATIONS

more realistic stacking sequence specimen (T_{12}) and a scaled specimen with increased width (T_{13}) will be tested.

TEST FACILITY

The cyclic load test rig is shown in Figure 3 and the ultrasonic NDE equipment is shown in Figure 4. This equipment, located at IITRI, is described more fully by Mr. K. E. Hofer of IITRI in Reference 1. The test rig can test up to five coupons simultaneously in a series chain and is controlled for load, temperature and humidity. The ultrasonic NDE can operate in either a through transmission or pulse-echo mode and will be used to track flaw growth.

ACCELERATED ENVIRONMENTAL TEST SPECTRUM

A typical random spectrum of the load and temperature history for the vertical tail (V.T.) of a supersonic aircraft is shown in Figure 5. This spectrum was derived from a metal V.T. spectrum. This single mission is the compilation of five utilization mission spectrum and shows the distribution of loads that are to be combined with skin temperatures on a percent of flight time. The load is presented as a load factor (L.F.) in terms of a ratio to limit load (or stress). The limit stress will vary at each structural point, or, in the case of these coupon tests, for each coupon type, material, and orientation. Since the loads for a vertical tail can be of equal magnitude in either direction, the spectrum contains a negative cycle equal to the positive cycle shown and are assumed to be applied sequentially. This produces the stress range value (R) equal to -1.0 . This typical mission contains 106.25 load cycles or a total of 135,000 per lifetime. This is a truncated spectrum, which in the metal V.T. had all cycles below a L.F. of .089 removed. This reduced the number of the test load cycles from an estimated total of 500,000 in a lifetime.

TEST SERIES	MATERIAL	LAMINATE	FLAW TYPE	FLAW SIZE	TEST CONDITION			LIFE TIMES				TOTAL SPECIMENS	NOTES		
					MOISTURE	FATIGUE TEMP	RESIDUAL TEMP	0	1	2	4(1)				
T ₁ /C ₁	A	1,2	0,1,2,3,4	A	DRY	RT	RT	3		3(2)		60 + 60			
T ₂ /C ₂		1,2	0,1,2,3,4	A	WET	REAL	HOT	3		3(2)		60 + 60			
T ₃ /C ₃		1,2	C ₁ & C ₂	B	DRY	RT	RT	3		3		24 + 24			
T ₄ /C ₄		1,2	C ₁ & C ₂	B	WET	REAL	HOT	3		3		24 + 24			
T ₅ /C ₅		1	0			DRY		-65	3					3 + 3	
T ₆ /C ₆			C ₁ & C ₂	C	DRY	REAL	-65	3		3				12 + 12	
			0			WET		-65	3					3 + 3	
T ₇ /C ₇		CRITICAL	A			DRY	RT	RT	2			5		7 + 7	
			B									5		7 + 7	
			C						5	5	5			15 + 15	
T ₈ /C ₈	CRITICAL	DRY	REAL	HOT	3		5					8 + 8			
T ₉ /C ₉	CRITICAL	WET	REAL	RT	3							3 + 3			
T ₁₀ /C ₁₀	A	A			WET	REAL	HOT	2		2	5	9 + 9			
		B						2	5	2	5	14 + 14			
		C						5	10	10		25 + 25			
T ₁₁ /C ₁₁	B	1	CRITICAL	CRITICAL	WET	REAL	HOT	5		5		10 + 10			
T ₁₂ /C ₁₂	A	1	CRITICAL	CRITICAL	WET	REAL	HOT	3	3	5		11 + 11			
T ₁₃ */C ₁₃ *	A	1	CRITICAL	CRITICAL	WET	REAL	HOT	3		3		6 + 6	2ND STACKING SEQUENCE INCREASE WIDTH TO 6 INCHES		
T ₁₄ /C ₁₄	A	1	0	0	WET	RT	RT	3		3		6 + 6	CONTROL FOR ELEMENT TESTS		
T ₁₅ /C ₁₅	A	1	0	0	DRY		HOT	3				3 + 3	CONTROL FOR ELEMENT TESTS		
B ₁	A	1	0,1,2,3	A	DRY	RT	RT	3		3(2)		24			
B ₂		1	0,1,2,3	A	WET	REAL	HOT	3		3(2)		24			
B ₃		1	C ₁ & C ₂	B	DRY	RT	RT	3		3		12			
B ₄		1	C ₁ & C ₂	B	WET	REAL	HOT	3		3		12			
B ₅			CRITICAL	A			DRY	RT	RT	2				5	7
				B						2				5	7
		C							5	5	5			13	
B ₆		CRITICAL	DRY	REAL	HOT	3		5	5	5		8			
B ₇		CRITICAL	WET		RT	3						3			
B ₈		1	CRITICAL	A			WET	REAL	HOT	2		2		5	9
			B						2	5	2	5		14	
			C						5	10	10			25	
B ₁₀	1	CRITICAL	CRITICAL	WET	REAL	HOT	3	3	5		11	2ND STACKING SEQUENCE INCREASE THICKNESS			
B ₁₁ *	1	CRITICAL	CRITICAL	WET	REAL	HOT	3		3		6	INCREASE THICKNESS			
B ₁₂	1	0	0	0	WET	RT	RT	3		3		6	CONTROL FOR ELEMENT TESTS		

*TEST CONDUCTED BY ROCKWELL

(1) OR UNTIL CRITICAL DAMAGE SIZE IS REACHED

(2) OR UNTIL DAMAGE GROWTH IS DISCERNIBLE BUT NOT GREATER THAN 4 LIFE TIMES

MATERIAL

A = AS3501-5A GRAPHITE EPOXY

B = T300/5208 GRAPHITE EPOXY

C₁ AND C₂ ARE THE TWO MOST CRITICAL FLAWS FROM SCREENING TESTS

ORIENTATION

1 = [(0/±45/90)₂]₂

2 = [(0/±45/0)₂]₂

FIGURE 2 COUPON TEST MATRIX

FIGURE 3 COUPON TEST RIG

FIGURE 4 COUPON NDE EQUIPMENT

LOAD FACTORS

NOTE: TOTAL LOAD CYCLES PER LIFE TIME = 500,000

FIGURE 5 SKIN TENSILE STRESS HISTORY

For the metal vertical tail, the maximum L.F. is .6265 of limit load. To create the worst case, which would encompass fighter, bombers and transports, the maximum load to be expected in a lifetime was raised to full limit load for these composite tests. Commensurately, all the other loads in the load spectrum were raised proportionately.

The accelerated load and temperature spectrum finally adopted for a simulated one life is shown in Figure 6. This shows the approximately 500,000 total load cycles compressed into 127,500 cycles and the nearly 4,000 low-high-low temperature excursions compressed into six cycles per lifetime. This severely reduced spectrum was required to allow one lifetime to be accomplished in a 24 hour test time span.

To consolidate to this accelerated spectrum, the spectrum was aggregated into segments of various temperatures and load levels for test convenience. Considering that there is one percent (1%) of the time temperature events, each authentic segment, 1/100 of a lifetime, would have to include 12.8 missions to contain the 1% temperatures. Thus there would be one-hundred segments, each containing six major temperature excursions. For this number of heat-up and cool-down excursions alone, 90 hours would be required per lifetime test. To reduce time, two further compromises were made: (1) rearranging the temperature sequences in a mission, and (2) revising the 1% to include the 9% temperature events, wherein the temperatures are adjusted to compensate. The first reduction was gained by reordering the mission temperature histories into monotonically increasing sequence from low to high to low as shown in Figure 7. The second reduction decreased the 100 segments to six. This reduced the 90 hours to 3.6 test hours per life for temperature transitioning, allowing nine minutes per excursion. This time, combined with 13.5 hours for load cycling at 3.0 and 0.5 Hertz, allowed 4.9 hours for setups and contingencies.

The load cycles likewise were aggregated and regrouped within each segment. The ordering of stresses in ascending severity was selected as coming

FIGURE 6 SEGMENTATION OF LOAD/TEMPERATURE CYCLES

FIGURE 7 TEMPERATURE HISTORIES EXPECTED IN A MISSION AND FIRST REARRANGEMENT

closer to simulating the effects of a random real-life experience (Ref. 2). This also allows for some efficiencies in programming the test controller. The number of extreme load and temperature combinations were retained, such as the 12 limit load experiences per lifetime. The truncation load factor now appears to be .192; but in aggregating the loads, those loads which were lower were combined at the .192 load level. Similarly, other load combining occurred in reducing from 32 load intervals to 15. However, the total number of cycles remained very nearly the same.

The selection of 3.0 and 0.5 Hertz as the cyclic test frequency was dictated by several considerations. It was desired that: (1) the wave form be sinusoidal; (2) the natural frequency of the test frame be well above the operating frequency; (3) the altering of the ratio of rise to peak stresses from flight experience would not produce noticeable or unrealistic effects which was confirmed by previous work (Refs. 3 and 4); (4) the cyclic frequency would permit reasonable test times; and (5) a lower frequency of 0.5 Hertz at the highest temperatures would extend the time at load where creep effects might contribute to degradation.

For the multi-life tests, the sequence of segments are as shown in Figure 8. The -65 to 270°F cycle is only repeated at the beginning of the third lifetime. Residual strength tests for the various test series are made at the end of one, two and four lifetimes as shown by the symbol \diamond . At the times shown by the symbol \circ , the chain is removed from the frame and an ultrasonic NDE is made to track the flaw growth. Other NDE checks are programmed to be made whenever the acoustic emission real time monitor gives any clue to excessive or a sharply increasing growth rate.

The final NDE, prior to the residual strength test, will be carefully and thoroughly performed to provide the most reliable definition of the flaws geometric characteristics. This aspect is crucial to assist in the theoretical prediction of residual strength and to prevent a source of error that would

FIGURE 8 MULTI-LIFE COUPON TESTING

otherwise be construed as analytical. And finally, to complete the description of the test condition, the coupons are preconditioned at 165°F and 98% relative humidity (R.H.) to an average 1.29% moisture content. To maintain this moisture during cyclic testing, the test chamber is raised to 95% R.H. during the 120 and 188°F heating cycles only. During the multi-lifetime tests, whenever the moisture levels fall below 80% of initial value, the coupons will be removed and reconditioned.

Figure 9 summarizes the compromises made in developing the accelerated environmental test condition. It is hoped that other current and future programs will put the significance of the risks taken in this effort in clearer perspective.

FLAW TYPES

To typify flaws in composites is still a nebulous undertaking due in part to the short span of experience and to a paucity of knowledge regarding their criticality on strength. Rockwell International summarized their own knowledge and in addition conducted an industry survey (Ref. 5). The more significant of the flaws defined by the survey are shown in Figure 10, classified by the manufacturing sequence in which they occur. This study screened the flaws to select four types for each of the three coupon types. Figures 11 through 17 cover these selections.

Because of the limited size of the coupon test section, there was some concern on the amount of influence the tabs and edges would have on the state-of-stress in the area of the flaw. It was not desired to perturb the stresses that would govern the flaw growth rate or residual strength. To substantiate these influences, Dr. Issac Daniels of IITRI performed an investigation of each flaw type using the Moire' technique, (Refs. 6 and 7). Moire' fringes for two of the tension coupon flaws are shown in Figure 18 at a stress level

COMPROMISES

- 500,000 CYCLES → 127,500 CYCLES

EFFECT: CLIPPING OF LOWER STRESS EXCURSIONS

- MONOTONICALLY ARRANGE TEMPERATURE EXCURSION

EFFECTS: REDUCES FREEZE-THAW OR LIQUID-STEAM CYCLES;
REORDERS STRESS/TEMPERATURE EXCURSIONS

- REDUCE SEGMENTS FROM 100 TO 6

EFFECT: REDUCES FREEZE-THAW OR LIQUID-STEAM CYCLES

- REDUCED DWELL TIME AT TEMPERATURE

EFFECT: MAY BE SIGNIFICANT (CREEP/RELAXATION)

NOTE: FREEZE-THAW CYCLES REDUCED FROM 10,000 TO 6
LIQUID-STEAM CYCLES REDUCED FROM 1,300 TO 6

FIGURE 9

CATEGORIZED FLAWS BY OCCURRENCE IN MANUFACTURING SEQUENCE

- FIBER & PREPREG GENERATION
 - PREPREG VARIABILITY EXCEEDS SPEC
 - RESIN STARVED
 - RESIN RICH
 - FOREIGN PARTICLES
 - PILLS OR FUZZ BALLS
 - (CONT)
- MACHINE LAMINATE
 - OVERSIZED HOLE
 - BREAKOUT
 - PULL THROUGH, COUNTERSINKS
 - OVERTORQUED FASTENER
 - (CONT)
- BASIC LAMINATE LAYUP
 - BLISTERS, DELAMINATIONS
 - EXCESS POROSITY
 - SCRATCHES FIBER BREAKAGE
 - SPLIT TOW
 - REWORKED AREAS
 - FOREIGN PARTICLES
 - DROPPED PLY
 - VARIABLE CURE
 - TOOL IMPRESSION
 - (CONT)
- BOLTING, FASTENER & ATTACHMENT
 - OVERSIZE HOLE
 - OUT OF ROUND HOLE
 - EDGE NOTCH
 - (CONT)
- BONDING & ADHESIVE PROCESSES
 - ADHESIVE STARVED
 - EXCESS POROSITY
 - FOREIGN PARTICLES
 - (CONT)
- FINAL ASSEMBLY & PAINTING
 - PAINT POROSITY, VOIDS
 - ETC

FIGURE 10

TENSION COUPON FLAW TYPES

FIGURE 11 FLAWED TENSION COUPON

FIGURE 12 FLAWED TENSION COUPON

COMPRESSION COUPON WITH FLAW TYPE 2
 (SAME STRESS FIELD AS FOR TYPE 1, BUT LOAD IS 22.5-DEGREES OFF-AXIS)

DIMENSIONS NOT SHOWN ARE TO BE SAME AS CORRESPONDING DIMENSIONS IN NO-FLAW COMPRESSION COUPON.

MAKE TAB IN SAME MANNER AS IN COMPRESSION COUPON WITH FLAW TYPE 1, AND LOCATE AT SAME POINT.

STACKING SEQUENCE 1:	-67.5	22.5	-22.5	67.5	-67.5	22.5	-22.5	67.5	67.5	-22.5	22.5	-67.5	67.5	-22.5	22.5	-67.5
STACKING SEQUENCE 2:	22.5	22.5	67.5	-22.5	22.5	22.5	67.5	-22.5	-22.5	67.5	22.5	22.5	-22.5	67.5	22.5	22.5
	BAG SIDE				CL								TOOL SIDE			

FIGURE 15 FLAWED COMPRESSION COUPON

COMPRESSION COUPON WITH FLAW TYPE 3
 (PLANAR DISPERSED STRESS GRADIENTS WITH LOCALIZED DISCONTINUITIES)

0.12 IN. TYPICAL

DIMENSIONS NOT SHOWN ARE TO BE SAME AS CORRESPONDING DIMENSIONS IN NO-FLAW COMPRESSION COUPON.

IN ALL STACKING SEQUENCES, SEPARATE (SPREAD) 3RD LAYER FROM BAG SIDE AND 4TH LAYER FROM TOOL SIDE WITH A 1/8-INCH GAP. LOCATE GAPS CENTRALLY AS SHOWN FOR SEQUENCES 1 AND 3 AS VIEWED FROM TOOL SIDE.

STACKING SEQUENCE 1:	90	0	GAP	-45	45	90	0	-45	45	45	-45	0	90	GAP	45	-45	0	90
STACKING SEQUENCE 2:	0	0	GAP	45	-45	0	0	45	-45	-45	45	0	0	GAP	-45	45	0	0
	BAG SIDE				CL								TOOL SIDE					

FIGURE 16 FLAWED COMPRESSION COUPON

COMPRESSION COUPON WITH FLAW TYPE 4

(LINEARLY DISPERSED STRESS GRADIENTS WITH LOCALIZED DISCONTINUITIES)

FIGURE 17 FLAWED COMPRESSION COUPON

FIGURE 18 MOIRÉ PATTERNS OF FLAWED TENSION COUPONS

approaching ultimate. As the fringes are nearly straight at the edge of the tabs, the influence of the tab is considered negligible at the area of the flaw. It is concluded that the test area geometry is barely adequate. In retrospect, a larger test area and higher aspect ratio would have been preferred; but any change would have required extensive changes to the test frame.

CONCLUSIONS

The program described is a serious endeavor made to evaluate the effect of some selective worst case defects on the safety and durability of composite structures. If under the expected worst case test conditions and flaw type, degradation does occur, then, hopefully, the bounds will be better defined as to: which flaw, type, size and location will grow in a critical mode; what are the critical type of loads and modes of failure; and the ability to detect and track critical flaws. Because of the compromises imposed on establishing the subject accelerated test conditions, further efforts will be required to evaluate the sensitivity of the parameters constrained on flaw growth and residual strength. The following are but a few of the technical aspects that are expected to require clarification: (1) further expanding the time at temperature to elucidate any creep effects on flaw growth; (2) investigation of the coupling of the freeze-thaw-hot cycle induced damage with flaw growth; and (3) improved definition of the minimum size flaws that could grow to catastrophic proportions within a specified number of lifetimes and require NDE detection.

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